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SYNTHESIS OF NEW PEPTIDES BASED ON NATURAL AND NON NATURAL AMINOACIDS POSSESSING *À LA CARTE* POLARITIES FOR SURFACE MODIFICATION OF NATURAL FIBERS

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Introduction: Basalt Fiber

- ✓ BF is a high performance inorganic silicate fiber, and generally fabricated by heating the basalt rocks and extruding molten liquid through a die in the form of fibers. Basalt rocks, suitable for BF production, are inexpensive and easy available around the world
- ✓ The basalt fiber market is projected to grow from USD 227 million in 2019 to USD 397 million by 2024, at a CAGR of 11.8% between 2019 and 2024. The market is growing due to the high demand from construction & infrastructure, automotive & transportation, and electrical & electronics end-use industries

Introduction: Basalt Fiber

Several efforts have been made to improve fiber/matrix interfacial adhesion, including functionalization of matrix, adding coupling agents, and surface modification of the fibers. All these methods could improve interfacial adhesion, contributing to a certain extent to an efficient stress transfer from the matrix to fibers

Silane treatment is a commercially available and cost-effective method for surface modification of fibers without destroying the structure and the properties of the fibers themselves or weakening fiber strength

Figure from *Polymers* 2017, 9(8), 351

Is it possible to
modify BF
without using a
binding agent?

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Introduction: ROP

M

- Really efficient
- Difficult to remove
- More than 1000!!

**Stereocontrol
polymerization**

- Not so efficient
- Easy to remove
- Less than 10-20 articles

Introduction: ROP

Nucleophile

**Nucleophilic
activator**

Base

Acid

Goal

NCA *N*-carboxyanhydride

Result

Epoxy BF: continuous roving of basalt fibers, supplied by Kamenny Vek, with a linear density of 1200 tex, nominal diameter of 13 μm and surface coated with a commercial sizing agent compatible with epoxy resin

Mafic BF: continuous roving of basalt fibers, supplied by Mafic, with a linear density of 450 tex, nominal diameter of 13 μm, no sizing

Result

Result

Result

Results

Result

H_2O_2/H_2SO_4
100 °C. 1h.

NCA (50 mg)
Toluene (7mL)
5 days

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Toluene (7mL)
5 days

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H_2O_2/H_2SO_4
100 °C. 1h.

NCA (50 mg)
Toluene (7mL)
5 days

MBF1

MBF2

MBF3

MBF4

SEM HV: 10.0 kV WD: 10.53 mm MIRA3 TESCAN
View field: 75.2 μm Det: SE 20 μm
SEM MAG: 11.0 kx Date(m/d/y): 11/30/18 Sapienza - Rome University

SEM HV: 15.0 kV SEM MAG: 14.2 kx MIRA3 TESCAN
View field: 48.6 μm Det: SE 10 μm
WD: 10.28 mm Sapienza - Rome University

SEM HV: 10.0 kV SEM MAG: 25.0 kx MIRA3 TESCAN
View field: 27.7 μm Det: SE 5 μm
WD: 8.95 mm Sapienza - Rome University

SEM HV: 15.0 kV SEM MAG: 10.0 kx MIRA3 TESCAN
View field: 69.2 μm Det: SE 20 μm
WD: 9.93 mm Sapienza - Rome University

Mafic-BF

Mafic-BF

TGA results

Mechanical properties of modified basalt fibers

- ✓ Reduced dispersion of data compared to untreated fibers
- ✓ Potential healing effect of polymer coating

Conclusions

- ✓ Two commercially available basalt fibers, i.e. Epoxy BF and Mafic BF, have been used as a substrate for surface polymerization reactions
- ✓ Commercial sizing on Epoxy BF prevents their surface modification
- ✓ Unsized Mafic BF were successfully modified after a pre-treatment ($\text{H}_2\text{SO}_4/\text{H}_2\text{O}_2$) aimed at increasing the presence of OH groups
- ✓ SEM micrographs, FT-IR spectra and TGA confirmed the presence of a polymer coating on the fiber surface, whose homogeneous coverage was found to increase with increasing reaction time
- ✓ Tensile strength of basalt fibers decreased compared to virgin fibers
- ✓ Compared to virgin fibers, the polymer coating was found to play a healing effect on surface defects thus reducing the dispersion of data as a function of reaction time

